

Next generation tools for accurate energy yield estimation of bifacial PV systems – best practices, improvements and challenges

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Introduction

Bifacial PV has recently gained great scientific and industrial interest thanks to its potential to reduce LCOE. A well-designed bifacial PV system can yield more energy per installed (front side) kWp due to light collection from the rear side. Rear side light collection can be achieved by a glass-glass module design, which is known to improve module reliability and extend module lifetime, reducing LCOE. The recent implementation of high efficiency c-Si cell technologies such as PERC and PERT enables solar cell bifaciality at little or no extra cost or energy, further reducing the LCOE and the environmental impact of the PV system. Moreover, glass-glass modules also increase illumination levels under the PV modules, which helps to rehabilitate ecosystems that were damaged during PV system installation [1]. In view of these facts it is not surprising that the ITRPV roadmap 2018 [2] predicts that the market share of bifacial PV might increase to almost 40% by 2028.

Nevertheless, the mass-deployment of this technology requires precise estimations of the revenues relying on accurate estimations of the energy production of the PV plant which is not possible with simulation tools optimized for monofacial systems because the albedo effect cannot be ignored. In the last couple of years, numerous research institutes and private entities have launched the development of diverse energy yield estimation tools for bifacial PV plants.

It is recognized that one of the most important elements in the precise energy yield assessment of bifacial PV systems is the resolution of the amount and non-uniform distribution of rear-side irradiance. The most accurate irradiance simulation approaches apply a view factor or ray-tracing method. The irradiance simulation results are used as inputs for physics-based thermal-electrical PV performance simulations e.g. by [3], [4], [5], [6] and [7]. To avoid the increasing computational complexity and runtime, most of the existing models attempt to simplify the bifacial PV module's response to ambient conditions by modelling a single, "typical" module within the array and then extrapolate the results to a full-size array. However, as a result of this, the impact of mismatch effects caused by spatial variations of bifacial irradiance is neglected. This assumption is only sufficiently accurate for estimating the current in a module in the middle position in the installation. However, the additional rear-side irradiance on other parts of the array induces non-negligible additional effects like increased heat generation, thus it should also be considered for an accurate PV yield assessment. The latter example showcases not only the underlying complexity of bifacial energy yield estimation but the insights into additional effects can also be used for a further optimization of the LCOE of PV systems by e.g. investigating how module lifetime varies across an array due to non-uniform operating temperatures. Thus, many elements of the bifacial system are directly and indirectly affecting the overall system performance.

In this paper, we address the complex challenges involved in the design and optimization of bifacial PV systems, including both temporal and spatial variations. We will focus on four main sub-domains of the energy yield estimation for bifacial systems; optical, thermal, electrical simulations and computational effort. IMEC's PV energy yield estimation framework, in combination with outdoor observation from various bifacial plants with different sizes, will be used to illustrate these various elements of the modelling flow and the importance of any of these elements on an accurate estimation of the LCOE of bifacial power plants and bifacial tracking systems. The overview, observation and recommendations serve as guidance for optimal bifacial system performance and performance estimation.

Rear-side irradiance modelling approach

The two most commonly applied approaches for optical simulation are View Factor (VF) method and Ray Tracing (RT). The VF method is based on several simplifying assumptions making it impractical for complex geometries [8] but enabling efficient computations. Its reported accuracy may reach +-10% (in bifacial PV systems) when compared to irradiance measurements using reference cells [8]. Ray Tracing is not limited by either complex geometry or complex physics, however, such calculations are known to be costly. The authors of [9] recommend to use Ray Tracing complementary to the View Factor method, exclusively for evaluating model sensitivity to features not treated by the View Factor approach.

In order to combine the accuracy of ray tracing with computational efficiency, the authors demonstrate the use of the Daylight Coefficient method for PV energy yield prediction [10]. The fundamental idea behind the Daylight Coefficient (DC) method is to perform a single ray tracing simulation instead of one at each time step (typically every 1 minute) of the simulation. That single ray tracing computation is used to establish a linear operator (called Daylight Coefficient Matrix), which transforms the sky radiance distribution into the irradiance distribution on the module surface (front or rear). Combining this approach with GPU computing, the computing time is reduced by a factor of 10^4 , meaning that high resolution irradiance simulations are now performed within a few minutes, without any loss of accuracy.

However, the simulation method itself is not the only important element; for an accurate irradiance estimation all the environmental elements, meaning reflecting or shadowing elements, specific reflection (specular and diffuse) of each element, exact orientation, etc., need to be considered. To demonstrate the importance of all those elements, we manufactured and installed bifacial PV modules on the rooftop of the EnergyVille 1 building in Genk (BE) in an optically challenging environment, meaning that the measurement site contains various reflecting and light-blocking elements with different reflection properties, as it is often the case for building-added flat roof PV systems. A picture of the measurement site (a photograph and a CAD drawing with the albedo factor of the various elements) is shown in Figure 1. More information about the manufacturing and characterization of the modules can be found in [11]. The energy production of the installed bifacial PV modules is measured every 15 s to capture also fast-varying irradiance effects [12]. Next to the performance monitoring system, various in-plane irradiance and module back-side temperature sensors have been added. 4 irradiance sensors monitor the front irradiance and 4 monitor rear irradiance, whereas their combination provides radiative albedo values. The sensor locations are indicated in Figure 1 (b), as well as the front (red) and rear facing (blue) plane.

Figure 1 - (a) picture of the measurement setup and (b) CAD drawing and albedo values for the same setup.

Source	Method	RMSE
Hansen et. al. [8]	VF	5-20%
Marion et al. [9]	VF	31%
Asg. et al. [13]	RT	4.3-16.4%
Deline et. al. [14]	RT	Up to 40%
Chiodetti et al. [4]	RT	5-20%

Figure 2 - RMSE (difference between sensor read-out and simulation result) for various elements in the front and rear side illumination estimation of the test structure for 36 mostly sunny days, and state-of-art estimation errors for back-side irradiance from sunny climates.

The sensor read-outs were used to identify the effect of each element in the environment and to provide experimental comparison to our irradiance modelling approach. A 3D ray-tracing model was built using the Daylight Coefficient-based approach as described above and the effect of various elements on the correctness of the estimation, evaluated in comparison with the sensors read-out, was characterized. To do so, we simulated the front and rear irradiance for a 36 days long period of September 2018 and compared the simulation results to measurements. The results are shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows the effect of the surrounding elements on both the front and back-side irradiance; all the elements impact the front-side irradiance, but especially the back-side irradiance is strongly affected by neglecting certain elements of the measurement structure. If only the PV modules are simulated, and all other surrounding elements are neglected, estimation errors up to 24% compared to measured rear-side irradiance occur. Implementing every surrounding element into the ray-tracing based irradiance simulation results in RMSE errors of the simulated versus the measured irradiance of 5.7%. This result represents state-of-the-art accuracy, as displayed by Table 1. Note that the best performance was obtained for the ray-tracing approaches. RMSE as low as 5% can be obtained using this method. However, all the surrounding elements and its optical properties need to be considered otherwise simulation errors will dominate the rear-side irradiance estimation. Calculating irradiance for all the solar cells in all modules of an array considering actual optical properties also enables the estimation of different loss contributions based on irradiance data alone. An example of a loss breakdown for a bifacial PV system is shown in Figure 3. This figure shows the analysis of both the total annual insolation and the bifacial gain for the system. Because of the non-uniform irradiance, not all the incident solar energy is harvested. More than 13% is lost as a combined result of glass reflections, bifaciality effects and cell and module mismatches. Taking all those elements into account results in bifacial gain of 7% compared to a potential gain of 16%. The analysis also shows that by e.g. reducing the module-to-module non-uniformities, in the analyzed PV system, one can gain 1.3%. The magnitude of mismatch losses of bifacial PV plants strongly depends on the system design. Figure 4 presents another system in Kuwait, which resembles in its design to a traditional monofacial PV plant.

Figure 3 - Loss break-down of bifacial PV system, based on irradiance modelling at a desert climate during 6 months from fall to spring

Figure 4 (right) includes the corresponding mismatch loss analysis, showing that such a PV stand consisting of multiple rows is more prone to high levels of mismatch losses due to enhanced self-shading. In this example, only ~50% of the additional solar energy is harvested due to mismatch losses between cells and modules. Since the loss contributions may strongly vary as a function of PV system design, one can use the described simulations to optimize bifacial PV system designs and performance, as described later in this paper.

Figure 4- Multi-row bifacial PV stand and the resulting impact of mismatch losses at different ground albedo values

Thermal modelling

As discussed in the introduction, an important effect is the additional heat generation of the PV modules induced by increased light-collection and non-uniform irradiation. In our approach, module operating temperatures are estimated using an RC equivalent thermal network, with elements equal to the specific heat capacity and resistivity of each layer of the PV module. Further, the thermal response of each solar cell is estimated using its dedicated thermal circuit and its I-V operating point. The current source that emulates the heat generation in this circuit is proportional to the sum of both the front and rear side irradiance, as extracted from the DC simulations and the intra-module optical model. Therefore, this approach integrates both the thermal effect of the non-uniform irradiance and the additional heating-up of the cell due to the extra light received from the rear. Previous studies revealed that neglecting such spatial thermal variations can result in a power estimation error of 4% [15]. This result was obtained by investigating the spatial effect of wind, however, a non-uniform back irradiance as shown on Figure 4 will result in a comparable estimation error. In a further extended full paper, we will report on the estimation error created by neglecting the thermal aspect of inhomogeneous elements like irradiance.

Thus, next to additional non-uniform irradiance on each module, also heat transfer mechanisms such as convective (due to natural convection and wind) and radiative cooling play important roles in the determination of the conversion efficiency. For an accurate estimation of the operating temperature, convective cooling effects as a function of wind speed, wind direction and PV module inclination and orientation are considered by implementing a model that treats all such dependencies [16]. In IMEC's modelling approach, wind effects are integrated by thermal equivalent resistors with varied values of resistance as a function of the wind speed and relative wind direction. The radiative losses are represented by the Boltzmann law and view factors of the ground and sky, which depend on module tilt angle. The importance of a correct description of both wind effect and radiative losses is demonstrated by Figure 5 (right). The figure shows how a bifacial PV module heats up during operation on a clear-sky day. After consecutive improvements of the wind effect and radiative cooling modelling (by implementing tilt angle dependency to the latter), the temperature deviation was reduced to max. 6 °C compared to measured values.

This temperature estimation improvement has a significant effect on annual energy yield estimation of bifacial PV systems: 3% energy yield reduction is concluded for a commercial bifacial PV system, originating from reduced conversion efficiency linked to higher operating temperatures at an average wind speed of 2m/s. This result brings the simulated energy yield closer to the actual yield of the plant. Note that all of this can be achieved without incurring an important computational overhead, thanks to the specific physics-based analytic modeling approach adopted in our framework.

Above, the effect of wind cooling on the operating temperature and the conversion efficiency is described for a fix-tilt bifacial PV system. The wind cooling effect is much more complex for tracking systems as tilt and orientation and thus effective cooling may vary throughout the day. Especially in this case, a correct calculation of wind effects is essential for an accurate energy yield estimation. Using 3D FEM models as demonstrated in [17], together with wind tunnel and field tests will all contribute to understanding and implementing the complex dependencies of wind cooling in our framework.

Figure 5 - (a) 2 different wind models, with red, a wind-tunnel derived model and blue, improved wind model based on [16] (b) measured and simulated backsheet temperature for various thermal models at a daily average wind speed of 2m/s. Ambient temperature is also shown. The green line shows the best estimation by using the improved wind model in combination with the radiative losses.

Electrical modelling

As the PV modules are affected by non-uniform irradiance, individual simulation (both thermally and electrically) of each PV module in the system is required. As described in the previous sections, module-specific irradiance is retrieved from Daylight Coefficient simulations and the spatially resolved solar cell temperature is simulated using thermal networks. For the electrical circuit, we propose to use single diode models to represent each module, to limit computational complexity and to enable a robust model parameter calibration process. For a realistic representation of mismatch effects, it is essential to implement module interconnections according to the string lay-out. To accelerate the computational process, we removed any need of circuit simulation by solving both the thermal and electrical equations in a few iterations. The front and rear irradiance are integrated with the module bifaciality factor to obtain the bifacial module’s effective irradiance, which implements the input of each diode model as current sources.

The electrical circuit model can be instantiated from either the datasheet of the PV module or using advanced IV measurements for various intensity and temperature conditions for both the front and rear side. The latter is the most accurate method, although datasheets also provide accurate results if both the bifaciality and low-light behavior are well described. A full characterization and model parameter extraction of the bifacial PV modules displayed in Figure 1 are presented in [11], demonstrating that properly calibrated single diode models indeed deliver satisfactory accuracy.

Bifacial PV plant optimization

One important challenge on the field of designing and optimizing the performance of bifacial PV plants is represented by the large number of design parameters and their inter-dependencies. Applying the presented modelling framework to optimizing bifacial PV plants allows the automatic optimization of a plant design to various objectives. One straightforward objective is to maximize annual energy yield, however, as the grid penetration of renewable energy sources increases it is possible that different types of objectives will arise e.g. related to optimal load matching.

Figure 6 – Initial design, list of optimization parameters and improved design on a bifacial PV plant

A bifacial PV plant optimization study has been performed, which makes use of an algorithm capable of constructing the entire power plant design based on high level input parameters such as PV stand layout, module elevation height, row

spacing, module spacing and module tilt. The optimization process is controlled by a gradient-based optimizer therefore the whole process is carried out automatically. The result of the optimization process is presented by Figure 6, which shows that ~4% energy production gain is obtained through the optimization process w.r.t. the initial design, which was conceived in accordance to the currently known bifacial PV plant design guidelines.

Comparing the initial and optimized designs presented in Figure 6 reveals how the optimizer adjusted the geometry: elevation height and inter-module spacing was increased, leading to reducing the self-shading effect. Such optimizations are enabled by the combination of the high accuracy and low computational overhead obtained in our modeling approach.

Conclusions

In this paper, we presented a brief review of best practices, improvement and challenges in PV energy yield modelling for bifacial PV plants. Over the years, numerous modelling approaches were developed for an accurate estimation of front and back-site irradiance on the PV modules. However, little attention was paid to the secondary effect of additional, non-uniform irradiance. Obviously, a correct estimation of the irradiance is the foundation of a precise assessment. It was shown that neglecting surrounding elements in irradiance simulation results in estimation errors up to 24%. We also demonstrated the importance of a correct simulation of the wind and radiative losses. Faulty temperature estimations can lead to annual energy yield estimation errors of 3% for a commercial PV system. Having an electrical model describing the individual cells is not only required for an accurate energy yield estimation, it is also useful to calculate potential bifacial PV module and PV systems. The detailed insights of the advanced tool can be used for a multi-objective system optimization of the annual energy yield or other parameters. Resolving fine details as described in this abstract may significantly increase the computational effort, which could be solved - as demonstrated - by combining the daylight coefficient method with GPU computing.

Outlook

Various aspects of a detailed PV energy yield simulation framework were demonstrated in this abstract. Unfortunately, not all the aspects could be detailed. At the conference, more details will be given about efficient GPU usage, spectrally resolved optical modelling and electrical model instantiation. The simulation results will be further supported by additional outdoor data from bifacial PV systems from various sizes and climates. By the time of the conference, additional features such as automated bifacial PV energy yield optimization and tracking devices will be integrated into the modelling framework.

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